

***MYCELIUM* + ABACA: PACKAGING THE FUTURE
SUSTAINABLY, ONE SPORE AT A TIME**

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Abstract – Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) foam's environmental persistence demands biodegradable alternatives. This study optimized *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium–sawdust composite reinforced with abaca (*Musa textilis*) fibers at 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% concentrations. The composites were evaluated for tensile strength, water absorption, and 12-week soil-burial biodegradation.

The non-abaca control exhibited the lowest tensile strength, while the 30% abaca composite achieved the highest value, demonstrating optimal reinforcement. All composites exhibited high water absorption ($\leq 354\%$), emphasizing the need for hydrophobic surface treatments. Decomposition rates decreased as abaca concentration increased, with the non-abaca mycelium control degrading fastest and the 50% formulation slowest. All composites degraded significantly faster than EPS foam ($p < 0.01$). Findings indicate that mycelium + 30% abaca forms a viable, fully biodegradable EPS replacement, provided moisture resistance is improved.

Keywords: Mycelium composite, Bio composites, Abaca reinforcement, *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium, Sustainable packaging.

CHAPTER I
INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study and Rationale of the Study

The increasing global demand for sustainable packaging materials has sparked the exploration of eco-friendly alternatives to conventional plastics, paperboard, and Styrofoam (Alemu et al., 2022). One promising solution is mycelium-based packaging, derived from fungal networks, which is biodegradable, low in environmental impact, and highly versatile (Krivanek, 2020). However, the widespread adoption of mycelium packaging has been limited by its relatively low mechanical strength and poor moisture resistance, which restricts its use in applications requiring durability and water resistance (Balaes et al., 2023).

Abaca fiber, a natural and abundant resource in the Philippines, is known for its high tensile strength, and resistance to saltwater degradation (Mari, 2019). These properties make abaca an ideal candidate for reinforcing mycelium-based materials. Despite its potential, limited research exists on integrating abaca fibers into mycelium composites, and there is a lack of understanding of how these fibers impact the mechanical and functional properties of the resulting material.

This study explores the potential of using abaca fiber reinforcement to enhance the mechanical properties of mycelium composites, specifically focusing on *Pleurotus*

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ostreatus mycelium. The research addresses key challenges, including tensile strength, and water absorption and aims to leverage the unique properties of abaca to create a high-performance, eco-friendly packaging material. The goal is to contribute to global sustainability efforts by promoting the use of locally sourced resources while advancing the adoption of mycelium-based packaging.

The environmental crisis caused by petroleum-based plastics, which account for over 50% of global plastic production (UNEP, 2018), has reached a critical point. Packaging materials alone contribute to 40% of total plastic waste (OECD, 2022). Among these, expanded polystyrene Styrofoam is particularly problematic due to its persistence in landfills, resistance to degradation, and toxicity when fragmented into microplastics (Little, 2022). Mycelium-based bio composites, derived from fungal growth on agricultural waste, offer a promising solution, thanks to their biodegradability, low energy footprint, and versatility (Biby et al., 2025). However, the commercial adoption of these materials is limited by inferior mechanical strength and poor water resistance compared to synthetic alternatives (Teeraphantuvat et al., 2024).

Integrating natural fibers like abaca *Musa textilis* into mycelium matrices may help address these limitations. Abaca fibers demonstrate a tensile strength of 980 MPa and an elastic modulus of 41 GPa, and their resistance to seawater degradation has led to their traditional use in marine cordage (Barba et al., 2020). While abaca has been widely studied in polymer composites, its integration into mycelium composites remains underexplored.

This study aims to fill these knowledge gaps by systematically evaluating abaca-reinforced *P. ostreatus* mycelium composites. Specifically, the research will investigate: (1) the optimal abaca fiber mixture (10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%) for enhancing mycelium composites, (2) the performance of these composites compared to non-abaca mycelium and low-density EPS foam composite in terms of tensile strength, and water absorption, and (3) their decomposition rates in natural environments. By leveraging the Philippines' abundant abaca and agricultural waste resources, this study seeks to develop eco-friendly packaging (bio composite) solutions that support global sustainability goals.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to evaluate the mechanical properties and biodegradability of abaca fiber-reinforced *Pleurotus ostreatus* composites for sustainable packaging applications.

Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the mechanical properties of mycelium + abaca composite prepared at the concentration of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% as compared to non-abaca mycelium composite in terms of:
 - 1.1. Tensile Strength;
 - 1.2. Water absorption?
2. What is the decomposition rate (in weeks) of the mycelium + abaca composite prepared at the concentration of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% as compared to

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non-abaca mycelium composite when buried in loam soil under natural environmental conditions at time intervals of:

2.1. 2 weeks;

2.2. 4 weeks;

2.3. 6 weeks;

2.4. 8 weeks;

2.5 10 weeks; and

2.6 12 weeks?

3. Is there a significant difference in the mechanical properties of mycelium + abaca composite prepared at the concentration of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% as compared to non-abaca composite?
4. Is there a significant difference in the decomposition rate of the mycelium + abaca composite prepared at the concentration of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% as compared to non-abaca composite all throughout time when buried in loam soil under natural environmental conditions?

Significance of Study

This study provides scientific data on mycelium-substrate interactions by analyzing how *Pleurotus ostreatus* colonizes abaca-reinforced substrates. It aims to determine the optimal abaca fiber ratio to improve the mechanical properties of mycelium-based bio composites, such as tensile strength, and water absorption, for use as sustainable packaging

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materials. The environmental impact of this bio composites will be analyzed through its decomposition rate.

On a local scale, this research contributes to the economic development of agricultural communities in Cavite, where white oyster mushrooms and abaca fibers can be locally sourced and cultivated. By introducing a value-added application for mushroom farming, beyond food production, the study opens new revenue streams for mushroom house growers. It has the potential to create employment in various stages of the production pipeline, including cultivation, fiber processing, composite molding, and packaging distribution. This aligns with rural development goals by strengthening Agri-based microenterprises and promoting circular bio economies in provincial settings. This is supported by PNS-BAFS 278:2019, Good Cultivation Practices (GCP) for Mushroom, which outlines recommended agricultural practices for mushroom cultivation and is listed among the approved Philippine National Standards (Department of Agriculture [DA] & Bureau of Agriculture and Fisheries Standards [BAFS], 2025). Additionally, the Explanatory Manual on Organic Crop Production defines standards for seed and crop production, including mushrooms, covering aspects such as wild harvest, postharvest, processing, handling, storage, and transport (Department of Agriculture [DA] & Bureau of Agriculture and Fisheries Standards [BAFS], 2022).

In terms of practical applications, the study supports the scalability and commercial viability of mycelium packaging. Major companies like Dell and IKEA have already begun integrating mycelium-based packaging into their supply chains. Dell, for example, has used mycelium packaging for cushioning electronics such as servers and laptops, reporting full

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composability within 45 days (Pierce, 2015). IKEA has also explored replacing Styrofoam with mycelium packaging in its furniture line, potentially reducing its packaging waste by up to 60% if implemented across all product categories (Bell, 2023). These examples demonstrate the product's market potential and relevance in the global shift toward eco-friendly packaging solutions.

In the context of global sustainability, this study directly contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goal 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) by promoting biodegradable packaging alternatives that reduce waste and reliance on fossil fuels. It supports SDG 13 (Climate Action) by offering a low carbon packaging solution, reducing greenhouse gas emissions associated with conventional plastics. Furthermore, the research indirectly supports SDG 15 (Life on Land) by minimizing terrestrial plastic pollution, which threatens biodiversity and soil health (United Nations Environment Programme [UNEP], 2021).

The novelty of this study lies in its focus on abaca (*Musa textilis*), a native Philippine fiber known for its tensile strength and moisture resistance. Unlike common reinforcements like jute or flax, abaca remains underexplored in mycelium composite applications. By investigating abaca's compatibility with *Pleurotus ostreatus*, the study introduces a new myco-material combination that is not only biodegradable but also locally abundant and culturally relevant. This innovation bridges fundamental mycological research with applied material science, offering both environmental and economic value through sustainable product design.

Scope and Limitations

This study aimed to improve the tensile strength, and water absorption, of mycelium-based packaging by reinforcing it with abaca fiber (*Musa textilis*). The study used *Pleurotus ostreatus* (Oyster mushroom) mycelium grown on a sawdust substrate, with varying proportions of abaca fiber, to determine the ideal mixture of abaca fiber and mycelium that resulted in the best enhancement of these properties. The effectiveness of the mycelium-abaca composite was compared to the non-abaca mycelium composite in terms of tensile strength, and water resistance (through water absorption test).

The study was limited to the use of abaca fiber as the reinforcement material for mycelium-based composites and did not explore other natural fibers. It used sawdust as the substrates for mycelium growth, with no alternative substrates considered. The study assessed the short-term (12-week) decomposition rate of the composite in loam soil, providing initial insights into its biodegradability, but did not address long-term decomposition patterns (Van Wylick et al., 2022). The decomposition study focused exclusively on monitoring the weight loss of the samples over 12 weeks, with measurements taken at two-week intervals. The loam soil was used in its natural state without any chemical or structural modification. No soil test analysis was performed prior to or during the decomposition experiment, which may have limited understanding of soil factors influencing biodegradation. The effects of extreme environmental conditions, such as high UV exposure or prolonged submersion in water, on the mechanical properties and decomposition rate of the composites were not assessed. The study was conducted under

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controlled laboratory conditions for mycelium inoculation and production, while natural environmental conditions were used for the decomposition study.

Cost analysis and considerations for large-scale manufacturing were excluded due to the exploratory nature of the research and limited access to industrial-scale production facilities. The research was also limited to packaging applications and did not investigate the use of mycelium-based composites in other areas like construction, textiles, food-grade packaging, or insulation, nor did it include health and safety testing, including toxicity and allergen assessments.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter compiles literature and studies relevant to mycelium-based packaging. The studies explored the properties, sustainability, and mechanical enhancements of mycelium composites, particularly with natural fiber reinforcements such as abaca. The information gathered will serve as a foundation for this research.

Mycelium-Based Packaging

Mycelium-based materials are recognized for their biodegradability and low environmental impact, offering a more sustainable alternative to synthetic packaging. Their use helps reduce waste and supports environmental preservation (Camilleri et al., 2025). These materials are lightweight, moldable, and possess natural insulation properties, making them suitable for various packaging applications. However, despite these advantages, mycelium-based composites often exhibit low tensile strength and poor water resistance, which limits their broader application in packaging (Alaneme et al., 2023).

The growth and structural properties of mycelium-based composites are influenced by several factors, with the type of substrate playing a critical role (Aiduang et al., 2024); The commonly used substrates for mycelium cultivation are sawdust. Research has shown that fiber (or substrate) processing methods, such as loose, chopped, or pre-compressed, and size have a greater impact on mechanical performance than their chemical composition (Elsacker et al., 2019). These findings suggest that variations in substrate materials

significantly influence the strength and durability of the final composite, ultimately affecting its suitability for packaging applications.

Certain fungal species, such as *Pleurotus ostreatus* (oyster mushroom), have been found to produce mycelium-based composites (MBCs) with strong mechanical properties, making them a promising option for sustainable packaging (Shin et al., 2025). These composites are formed by cultivating fungal mycelium on lignocellulose substrates, creating materials that are both sturdy and biodegradable (Gan et al., 2022). Continued research into optimizing fungal species, substrate selection, and reinforcement strategies is essential for improving the performance of MBCs and expanding their application in packaging.

Mechanical Properties of Mycelium Composites

Factors such as fungal species, substrate type, and processing conditions influence the mechanical properties of mycelium-based materials. Studies suggest that incorporating natural fibers into mycelium composites can significantly improve their tensile strength, making them more suitable for packaging applications (Aiduang et al., 2024).

Research has shown that fiber reinforcement enhances both the flexibility and toughness of mycelium composites. Additionally, comparisons of different natural fibers indicate that the type of reinforcement material plays a significant role in influencing these mechanical properties (Voutetaki & Mpalaskas, 2024).

However, a major limitation of mycelium composites is their susceptibility to moisture absorption. Due to their naturally porous and hydrophilic nature, these materials

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readily absorb water, which can weaken their structural integrity and mechanical properties. Studies have shown that prolonged water exposure leads to swelling and degradation, reducing their durability. This issue is especially concerning in high-humidity environments, where moisture sensitivity further limits their application in packaging (Gezer et al., 2024).

One approach to addressing this challenge is the integration of natural fibers into the mycelium matrix. Natural fibers act as reinforcement, improving tensile strength and fracture resistance while also contributing to better moisture resistance. By enhancing the composite structure, fiber reinforcement helps mitigate the negative effects of water exposure, making mycelium-based materials more durable for packaging applications (Voutetaki & Mpalaskas, 2024). Another approach is coating mycelium composites with hydrophobic substances, such as beeswax or hydrophobic resins, to create a moisture barrier. Research indicates that increasing the proportion of beeswax in the coating enhances the water-repellent ability of mycelium-based composites due to the hydrophobic nature of beeswax. This coating method can significantly reduce water absorption, further improving the durability and functionality of mycelium-based packaging materials (Ahmad Farrahnour et al., 2024).

Regarding water resistance, according to the Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (NWO), Mycelium composites can easily absorb water because they have a structure with tiny holes that make them sensitive to moisture. The research conducted by Gezer et al. (2024) found that fiberboards made from mycelium absorbed

more water and swelled more in thickness than the control boards made with adhesives, a trade-off for being a more sustainable, biodegradable material.

The highest water absorption levels were observed in mycelium-based composites (MBCs) made from rice straw, followed by those produced from corn husks and sawdust. Also, mycelium-based composites (MBC) show that a lower density can lead to poorer vapor and moisture control because of extended colonization periods (Monsalve, 2025).

Comparison with Conventional Packaging Materials

Mycelium-based packaging materials are gaining attention as sustainable replacements for traditional packaging materials like expanded polystyrene (EPS), commonly known as Styrofoam. While both materials serve similar functions, they exhibit distinct differences in strength, flexibility, and moisture resistance (Enarevba & Haapala, 2023).

Corporate Adoption of Mycelium-Based Packaging

Mycelium-based packaging has gained significant attention as a sustainable alternative to conventional packaging materials. Large corporations, including Dell and IKEA, have explored the potential of mycelium composites to replace petroleum-based foams and Styrofoam. A review highlighted the growing interest of these companies in adopting mycelium-based packaging due to its biodegradability, mechanical strength, and low environmental impact (Jones et al., 2019).

Abaca Fiber Reinforcement in Bio composites

Abaca fibers, derived from *Musa textilis*, are known for their high tensile strength, and moisture or water resistance, making them a promising reinforcement material for bio composites. These natural fibers serve as a sustainable alternative to synthetic reinforcements, improving the mechanical properties of composites while promoting environmental sustainability. A study on bio-based high-density polyethylene (BioPE) composites reinforced with abaca fibers highlighted the importance of evaluating flexural strength alongside tensile properties to fully understand the mechanical performance of these materials (Seculi et al., 2023). Similarly, research on abaca–glass fiber hybrid composites produced through the vacuum assisted resin transfer method demonstrated that combining abaca with glass fibers enhances mechanical properties, suggesting potential applications in the automotive and construction industries (Paglicawan et al., 2021). These findings indicate that natural fiber reinforcement holds great potential for sustainable material development. However, a thorough mechanical evaluation and strategic hybridization are necessary to optimize performance, supporting the broader use of natural fiber composites in structural and industrial applications.

Beyond synthetic bio composites, studies have also explored the integration of natural fibers like hemp and jute into mycelium composites, which have been shown to improve their strength and durability. The addition of these fibers to mycelium matrices enhances mechanical properties such as strength, flexibility, and overall durability (Voutetaki & Mpalaskas, 2024). Comparative studies have further demonstrated that different natural fibers influence the mechanical properties of mycelium-based composites

in varying ways. Understanding these effects is essential for selecting the most suitable fibers to optimize the strength, flexibility, and durability of sustainable materials. These findings reinforce the potential of fiber-reinforced mycelium composites as viable alternatives for applications requiring improved mechanical performance.

In addition, studies demonstrate that cellulose-rich fibers like hemp enhance substrate porosity and moisture retention, facilitating faster, more uniform hyphal colonization (Voutetaki & Mpalaskas, 2024), while frameworks such as rattan provide structural reinforcement, enabling load-bearing capabilities exceeding 20x the composite's weight (Nguyen et al., 2022). Although there are no studies that have focused on abaca fibers yet, their similar makeup suggests they might help in the same way as other fibers for growth of mycelium and performance in composites.

On abaca fiber length selection as a reinforcement for mycelium composites, the study by Tampi et al. (2024) offers insights. Their work with concrete composites demonstrated that 50 mm abaca fibers provided optimal reinforcement, increasing tensile strength by 18% and flexural modulus by 22% compared to shorter fibers. This length balanced two critical factors: (1) sufficient surface area for effective stress transfer between fibers and matrix, and (2) minimized fiber entanglement that could compromise material homogeneity. While their research focused on concrete, these findings suggest a transferable principle for natural fiber reinforcement in biological matrices. For mycelium composites, 50 mm fibers may similarly optimize the balance between hyphal penetration depth and fiber dispersion, making this length a scientifically justified starting point for the investigation of abaca-mycelium composites.

***Pleurotus ostreatus* Mycelium Inoculation and Growth**

In mushroom cultivation, proper substrate sterilization is essential to eliminate competing microorganisms that can hinder yield (Sidik et al., 2015). Grimm et al. (2024) found that autoclaving substrates at 121°C significantly improved dry yields of oyster mushrooms by up to 50% compared to pasteurization techniques. Autoclaving at 121°C for 60 minutes has significantly lower contamination rates and supports mycelial colonization than hot water treatment (Sales-Campos et al., 2021).

Temperature during the incubation period significantly affects the mycelial growth of *Pleurotus ostreatus*. Studies show 25°C promotes the fastest growth compared to 20°C or 30°C (Ghavimi et al., 2024). At this temperature, complete substrate colonization occurs in 14 days, while fluctuating temperatures (3-19°C) require 22 days (Tesfaw et al., 2015).

Darkness has also been shown to support optimal mycelial development in *Pleurotus ostreatus* during incubation (Krupodorova et al., 2024). It has been a standard cultivation practice, as light can trigger reproductive processes that may interfere with consistent vegetative growth. Further study demonstrated that mycelial growth and fruiting body initiation of *Pleurotus ostreatus* can occur in continuous darkness (Amirtham et al., 2022)

Additionally, drying temperature significantly influences the physical and mechanical properties of mycelium-based composites. A study published in the *Pertanika Journal of Science and Technology* (2025) found that oven drying at 60 °C for 24 hours produced composites with superior flexural strength, modulus, and impact resistance

compared to those dried at higher temperatures. Increasing the drying temperature beyond 60 °C led to a decline in mechanical performance, which was attributed to the possible thermal degradation of the mycelial network.

Sawdust as Mycelium Substrates

The mushroom-forming organism naturally grows on agricultural waste materials such as sawdust, wood chips, and other organic and inorganic substrates. Many researchers have noted that the type of organic substrate influences the properties of the fungal mycelium produced after colonization. Key characteristics, including tensile strength, density, and water holding capacity of the fungal-based mycelium, can vary depending on the substrate used. (Alamene et al., 2023).

Sawdust is commonly used as a substrate due to its favorable physical properties, such as porosity and water retention capacity. According to the Observatory of Economic Complexity (OEC), in 2023, the Philippines exported approximately \$919,000 worth of sawdust, wood waste, or scrap, positioning it as the 59th largest exporter of these materials globally. This export data reveals an abundant yet underutilized domestic resource that could be repurposed for mycelium composite production. Sawdust as a substrate alone took 21 days to colonize a 10×12 cm polyethylene bag and was found to be a suitable substrate for cultivating *Pleurotus ostreatus* (Orngu, 2021).

Moisture content is essential for the effective cultivation of mycelium, as it significantly affects colonization speed, enzymatic activity, and overall growth. A study conducted by Wiesnerová et al. (2023) investigated how varying water content levels in

wheat straw pellets influenced the growth of *Pleurotus ostreatus*. Their findings indicated that the optimal water content lies between 65% and 75%, with the highest enzymatic activity and biological efficiency observed at 75%. Although the study centered on wheat straw pellets, it emphasizes the broader significance of ensuring adequate moisture in substrates, applicable to other lignocellulosic materials such as sawdust.

Decomposition Study

Biodegradability is a key advantage of mycelium-based composites, making them a sustainable alternative to conventional packaging materials. Mycelium-based composite (MBC) naturally decomposes because of its organic structure, with fungal hyphae serving as the main binding agent that disintegrates through microbial action (Ghazvinian, 2022).

Several studies have examined the degradation process of mycelium-based materials under different environmental conditions, particularly in soil. A study by Van Wylick et al. (2022) on the decomposition rates of various mycelium-based composites over 16 weeks assessed weight loss percentages at multiple intervals, including 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 16 weeks. In this study, samples were encased in nylon mesh and embedded in potting soil with a grain size of 2 mm and with a pH ranging between 6 and 7. Findings indicated that pure mycelium samples exhibited approximately 50% weight loss after 16 weeks (112 days) of soil burial.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between the independent variable, process variables, and dependent variables measured in the study. It provides a visual roadmap that guides the research in evaluating the effects of different abaca fiber mixture concentrations on the tensile strength, water absorption, and biodegradability of *Pleurotus ostreatus*-based mycelium composites grown on sawdust substrate.

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework

The independent variable are the abaca fiber concentration (0% or non-abaca, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50%). The fibers were incorporated into the sawdust substrate and colonized by *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium to form the bio composite material.

In the processing of the bio composite, sterilization (121 °C for 60 minutes), incubation conditions (25 °C, 50% relative humidity), and moisture content (65–75%) are

controlled factors. While, the dependent variables measured include tensile strength, water absorption, and decomposition rate.

Measuring these variables allows assessment of whether increasing abaca fiber concentration effectively enhances the tensile strength and water resistance while maintaining or improving biodegradability compared to non-abaca mycelium bio composites.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined operationally to provide a common frame of reference for this study.

Abaca Fiber *Musa textilis*. In this study, abaca fiber is used as a natural reinforcement material added at different concentrations (10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50%) to strengthen the mycelium-based composite. It is evaluated for its effect on the composite’s tensile strength, stiffness, and water resistance.

Bio composite. Referring to the material developed by combining *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium with sawdust substrate and abaca fibers. In this study, it serves as the main product tested for its strength, durability, water resistance, and biodegradability as an eco-friendly packaging material.

Non-Abaca Composite. Referring to the controls which provided the baseline for evaluating the effects of abaca reinforcement. These included the non-abaca mycelium–sawdust composite, and low-density EPS foam (commercial benchmark) for tensile strength and biodegradability comparison.

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Biodegradability. The ability of the mycelium–abaca composite to naturally break down in loam soil through microbial activity. It is measured by the percentage of weight loss of the samples every two weeks for a total of 12 weeks.

Colonization Speed. The number of days required for *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium to completely cover the substrate-fiber mixture.

Loam Soil. The type of soil used in the biodegradability test. It was chosen because it contains natural microorganisms and nutrients that help simulate real environmental conditions for decomposition.

Moisture Content. The amount of water present in the substrate before inoculation. It is controlled within 65–75% because it affects how well the mycelium can grow and spread during colonization.

Mycelium *Pleurotus ostreatus*. The vegetative part of the oyster mushroom that acts as a natural binder in the composite. It grows through the substrate and abaca fibers, binding them together to form a solid biodegradable material.

Sawdust. Wood processing residue is used as the substrate for mycelium growth to form the bio composite.

Tensile Strength. The maximum force that the mycelium–abaca composite can withstand when being stretched before breaking. It helps determine how strong the composite is compared to Styrofoam and non-abaca composites.

Water Absorption. The amount of water the mycelium–abaca composite takes in when soaked. It measures the composite’s water resistance, which is important for packaging applications.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the procedures used in the conduct of the study. It included the research design, research locale, and the materials and equipment used during the experimentation.

Research Design

This study utilized a single-factor experimental design to determine the effect of abaca fiber concentration on the mechanical properties and biodegradability of mycelium-based composites. The independent variable was abaca fiber concentration with six treatment levels: 0% (non-abaca control), 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50%. For mechanical comparison, low-density EPS foam was included as a positive control. The dependent variables included tensile strength, water absorption, and decomposition rate. The sawdust substrate was kept constant throughout all procedures to ensure consistent growth conditions for *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium.

Figure 2

Abaca fiber concentrations used for mycelium composites

(a) 0% (non-abaca control); (b) 10% Abaca; (c) 20% Abaca; (d) 30% Abaca; (e) 40% Abaca; (f) 50% Abaca; and (g) Low -density EPS foam (control).

Research Locale

The experiments were conducted across three facilities. (1) The Lyceum of the Philippines University-Cavite (LPU-Cavite) Biology Laboratory served as the primary site for substrate preparation, sterilization, and mycelium cultivation, with environmental conditions maintained at 25–28°C. (2) A Residential House in Brgy. Manggahan General Trias Cavite was utilized for the decomposition testing phase of the study. (3) For the mechanical properties testing phase, selected tests (tensile strength, and water absorption) were performed at the Department of Science and Technology – Forest Products Research and Development Institute (DOST-FPRDI) Laboratory, which houses standardized equipment for materials testing.

This multi-site approach ensured that each investigation stage, from mycelium cultivation to tensile and water absorption testing, and decomposition study, maintains experimental consistency.

Figure 3

Methodology Overview

Materials and Equipment

***Pleurotus ostreatus* Mycelium:** The *Pleurotus ostreatus* var. florida (White oyster mushroom) was obtained from Central Luzon State University, Mycosphere laboratories. The Florida variation was chosen for its white *mycelium*, ensuring visual appeal in final composite products.

Substrate: The sawdust substrate was obtained from a local lumber mill at San Clemente, Tarlac.

Abaca fiber: Abaca fibers (*Musa textilis*) were sourced from a local supplier, UgoyPh via Lazada online store. The fibers will be chopped to 50 mm long following Tampi et al (2024). The abaca fibers were used without any chemical or thermal treatment.

Loam soil: Used for the decomposition study, was sourced from *The Dirty Gloves PH* via Shopee.

Styrofoam (low-density EPS foam): Commercial-grade Styrofoam sheets (150 × 25 × 10 mm) will be purchased from a local hardware store and used as a control.

Composite Preparation

The sawdust substrate was sterilized by autoclaving at 121 °C for 60 minutes, following Sales Campos et al. (2021). Separately, raw abaca fibers were cut into 50 mm lengths using stainless steel scissors and were sterilized using the same autoclave parameters. Once sterilized and cooled to room temperature, distilled water was added incrementally to adjust the substrate's moisture content to about 70%, within the recommended range of 65–75%, as stated by Wiesnerová et al. (2023). Before inoculation, the moisture level was checked using the wet weight–dry weight method.

Figure 3

Moisture Content Formula

$$\mu = \frac{(\text{weight before} - \text{weight after})}{\text{weight after}} \times 100 = \text{moisture content in \%}$$

The sterilized substrate was mixed with abaca fibers at varying concentrations of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% by weight. Each mixture was inoculated with *Pleurotus*

ostreatus grain spawn at a 10% weight-to-weight ratio under sterile conditions inside a laminar flow hood. The inoculated substrates were packed into pre-sterilized 20 cm × 28 cm zip-lock bags, which had been sterilized using UV light exposure for 15–30 minutes prior to use, following the procedures of Kowalski (2009) and Zhang et al. (2016). The bags were incubated at 25 °C in complete darkness. Full colonization was expected within the typical 14–21-day period (Tesfaw et al.) for *P. ostreatus* on sawdust-based substrates, and the bags were monitored daily until complete mycelial coverage was achieved.

Fully colonized substrates were transferred into standard baking pan molds (30 × 20 × 5 cm) for mechanical and water resistance testing. The material was manually compressed to achieve a uniform density ranging from 0.3–0.5 g/cm³ and shaped according to mold dimensions. Aluminum trays were used to provide structural support during this process.

The molded composites were then heat-treated at 60 °C for 24 hours in a drying oven to deactivate the mycelium. Afterward, the samples were air-dried and stored at ambient laboratory conditions (25 °C, 50% relative humidity). The final composite specimens were trimmed to precise dimensions using a sharp blade in preparation for the mechanical and water resistance tests.

Figure 4

Composite preparation, inoculation and molding of abaca-mycelium composites

(a) Rice straw substrate and *Pleurotus ostreatus* inoculum (b) Inoculation of *P. ostreatus* in rice straw substrate with varying abaca concentration; (c) Molding of inoculated mycelium (d) Storing of abaca-mycelium composites.

Mechanical Testing

All samples were conditioned for seven days at room temperature (25 °C) before testing. Both the tensile strength and water absorption tests were conducted using three replicates per treatment to ensure measurement reliability and allow statistical comparison across composite formulations. The tensile strength and water absorption tests were conducted at the DOST-FPRDI laboratory using standardized procedures.

Tensile Strength

The tensile strength of the mycelium–abaca composites was determined using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) following the ASTM D1037-12 standard. The test specimens measured 5 × 5 cm and were cut from the molded composite. The machine applied a constant crosshead speed of 0.16 in/min until the specimen fractured. The maximum tensile stress (MPa) was recorded for each sample. This test evaluated how the addition of abaca fiber affected the composite’s tensile strength compared to the non-abaca composite.

Water Absorption

The water absorption of the mycelium–abaca composites was determined based on PNS ISO 16893:2017, which specifies the method for measuring water absorption of wood-based panels. Specimens measuring 5 × 5 cm were oven-dried at 60 °C for 24 hours to obtain the initial dry weight (W₀). The samples were then immersed in distilled water at 23 ± 2 °C for 24 hours. After immersion, the specimens were removed, surface-dried, and weighed again to determine the wet weight (W₁). The percentage of water absorption was calculated using the formula:

Figure 5

Water Absorption Formula

$$\text{Increase in weight, \%} = \frac{\text{wet weight} - \text{conditioned weight}}{\text{conditioned weight}} \times 100$$

Decomposition Study

The biodegradability of the abaca–mycelium composites was evaluated through a soil burial test to determine the material’s decomposition rate under natural conditions. The procedure followed the guidelines of European standard ISO 20200 for evaluating the disintegration of plastic materials under simulated composting conditions.

Sample Preparation

Pre-weighed abaca-mycelium composites (5 x 5 cm) were oven-dried at 70°C for 5 to 10 hours to remove moisture following Elsacker (2019) and determine initial dry weight (W_0). Each sample will be tagged for identification and will be wrapped in nylon mesh to contain the material while allowing direct exposure to soil, moisture, and microorganisms.

Burial Procedure

A total of 12 samples were tested, consisting of 2 replicates. The samples included six (6) variations of abaca mixture at concentrations of 0%(non-abaca mycelium control), 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50%. The samples were buried at a depth of 20 cm in loam soil, which was first sieved using a ≤ 2 mm mesh to remove debris and ensure uniform texture. The soil was placed in a large plastic container and kept at a Residential House in Brgy. Manggahan General Trias Cavite, where it was exposed to natural temperature and humidity conditions throughout the testing period. The setup was protected from heavy rainfall and direct sunlight using a mesh cover to prevent disturbances. This location was

selected for its accessibility and consistent environmental exposure (temperature, and humidity), which mirrors real-world conditions where biodegradable materials decompose. While the setup does not control external factors, the area allows for regular monitoring and minimizes interference from human or animal activity, ensuring consistency with the observation.

Decomposition Measurement

The decomposition test was conducted over a 12-week period, with samples retrieved every two weeks (Weeks 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12). After excavation, soil particles were gently brushed off, and the samples were oven-dried at 70 °C for 5 to 10 hours to remove moisture before weighing. The final weight (W_f) was recorded, and the percentage of weight loss, representing the decomposition rate, was calculated using the formula:

Figure 6

Biodegradation assessment of Abaca-mycelium composites within a 12-week period

(a) Samples wrapped in a nylon mesh for soil-burial (b) Soil burial setup; (c) Excavation of buried samples for decomposition rate assessment (d) Oven drying of excavated samples for weight loss assessment.

Figure 7

Weight loss (Material Degradation)

$$W_{\text{loss}} \% = \frac{W_0 - W_1}{W_0} \times 100$$

Decomposition rates were compared among abaca-mycelium composites with varying fiber ratios, and non-abaca composites to evaluate differences in biodegradability.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, standard error) will be calculated for all variables. Normality of data will be checked using the Shapiro-Wilk test, and homogeneity of variances will be assessed using Levene's test. A two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) will be used to determine the effects of abaca fiber concentration and substrate type on the mechanical properties (tensile strength, water absorption) and decomposition rate of the composites. If significant interactions are found, post-hoc Tukey's HSD tests will be conducted to determine significant differences between treatment groups. If the data do not meet the assumptions of ANOVA, non-parametric tests (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's post-hoc test) will be used. Statistical significance will be defined as $p < 0.05$. Regression analysis will be used to model the relationship between abaca fiber concentration and mechanical properties.

**CHAPTER IV
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

This chapter presents the experimental data generated from evaluating the tensile strength, water absorption, and decomposition rate of mycelium composites reinforced with varying concentrations of abaca fiber. The results highlight the effects of abaca fiber reinforcement on the tensile strength, water absorption, and decomposition rates of *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium-based composites. Comprehensive discussions accompany each section by interpreting the findings in the context of sustainable packaging applications and relevant literature.

Tensile Strength Analysis

The tensile strength analysis assesses how different abaca fiber concentrations (10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50%) influence the tensile strength of the mycelium composites compared to non-abaca reinforced mycelium and low-density EPS foam. This section presents quantitative tensile strength values and explores the role of fiber reinforcement in enhancing composite durability and perpendicular stress resistance.

Table 1

Tensile Strength (Internal Bond) Test Report

Specimen Group	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	Mean (kg/cm ²)
Low-Density EPS Foam Control	14.80	14.23	13.97	14.33
Non abaca Mycelium Composite Control	0.92	0.12	0.14	0.39
10% Abaca Mycelium Composite	3.06	3.57	2.75	3.13
20% Abaca Mycelium Composite	1.84	5.72	6.12	4.56
30% Abaca Mycelium Composite	8.67	8.36	9.08	8.70
40% Abaca Mycelium Composite	4.39	5.71	7.34	5.81
50% Abaca Mycelium Composite	4.39	4.18	4.90	4.49

As seen in table 1, the non-abaca mycelium composite control demonstrated minimal cohesion, recording the lowest mean tensile strength of 0.39 kg/cm². This baseline value reveals the limitations of the *Pleurotus ostreatus* fungal composite when grown solely on a sawdust substrate, without fiber reinforcement.

The incorporation of abaca fibers resulted in a progressive enhancement of tensile strength up to a specific threshold. The 10% Abaca formulation yielded a mean of 3.13 kg/cm², representing an increase over the non-Abaca mycelium control. This trend continued with the 20% Abaca group with a mean of 4.56 kg/cm². However, the most notable result was observed in the 30% Abaca mycelium group, which achieved a peak mean tensile strength of 8.70 kg/cm². This represents a 22-fold increase in tensile strength over the non-abaca mycelium composite, identifying 30% as the optimal fiber loading. This

peak suggests that at this specific ratio, the Abaca fibers efficiently distribute stress and are fully encapsulated by the fungal network. The observed increase in tensile strength with abaca loading, peaking at 30%, agrees with Seculi et al. (2023) that show abaca possesses notable tensile strength and acts as an effective reinforcement for composites.

Beyond the 30% abaca-mycelium composite, a decline in mechanical performance was evident. The 40% Abaca and 50% Abaca groups recorded mean tensile strength values of 5.81 kg/cm² and 4.49 kg/cm², respectively. This decline in tensile strength at higher abaca loadings suggests the presence of a saturation point, where excessive fiber content disrupts the formation of a continuous fungal network. Such fiber crowding is known to diminish matrix-to-fiber adhesion and promote void formation, ultimately weakening the composite's internal bond (tensile strength). This phenomenon is consistent with Paglicawan et al. (2021), who found that in abaca-reinforced glass fiber composites, increasing natural fiber content beyond the optimal threshold resulted in decreased tensile properties due to compromised matrix continuity and interfacial bonding.

In comparison to the commercial standard, the optimized 30% biocomposite reached 60% of the mean tensile strength of the Low-Density EPS Foam control (14.33 kg/cm²). While not fully matching the synthetic (EPS foam) standard, this demonstrates that the 30% Abaca formulation is a structurally viable alternative for sustainable packaging applications requiring moderate tensile strength.

Water Absorption Assessment

Water absorption tests provide insight into the composite's resistance to moisture uptake, a critical factor for packaging performance. This section discusses how abaca fiber integration affects the mycelium composite's hydrophilic nature and the implications for its water resistance and potential applications in humid environments.

Table 2

Water Absorption Test Report

Specimen Group	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	Mean (%)
Low-Density EPS Foam Control	1.59	2.34	1.12	1.68
Non abaca Mycelium Composite Control	251.24	312.36	306.28	289.96
10% Abaca Mycelium Composite	216.61	186.53	259.75	220.96
20% Abaca Mycelium Composite	202.43	280.17	257.39	246.66
30% Abaca Mycelium Composite	282.84	328.33	274.85	295.34
40% Abaca Mycelium Composite	341.97	301.25	232.08	291.77
50% Abaca Mycelium Composite	354.63	337.22	188.68	293.51

In table 2, the Low-Density EPS Foam control performed as expected for a closed-cell polymer, exhibiting a Mean WA of 1.68. In contrast, all mycelium-based formulations exhibited high moisture susceptibility.

The baseline non-abaca mycelium composite control recorded a Mean WA of 289.96%, demonstrating that the porous, non-abaca mycelium composite readily absorbs

moisture. Although, the introduction of 10% Abaca-mycelium composite achieved the lowest WA (220.96%) among the biocomposites, the overall increase in fiber loading failed to provide effective water resistance. The Mean WA values for the higher-loading groups, 30% (295.34%), 40% (291.77%), and 50% (293.51%), are proximate to the non-abaca mycelium composite control. This suggests that the increasing Abaca concentration exerts a limited influence on the composite's water absorption. According to Gezer et al. (2024), mycelium-based composites are inherently porous and highly hydrophilic, resulting in pronounced moisture. In our study, the consistently elevated water absorption values, even with fiber reinforcement, reflect this characteristic. The physical properties of the untreated mycelial-sawdust matrix, their open pore structure and affinity for water, are the main factors controlling moisture absorption.

The 30% Abaca mycelium composite, despite achieving optimal tensile strength, recorded the highest mean WA of 295.34%, placing its moisture uptake on par with the non-abaca mycelium composite. Furthermore, consistency severely declined at the highest concentration. The 50% Abaca composite exhibited extreme variability among replicates, with absorption values spanning from 188.68% to 354.63%. This wide range suggests unpredictable structural uniformity within the material, posing a critical quality control risk for manufacturing reliability.

Decomposition Rate Evaluation

The biodegradability of the mycelium-abaca composites was examined through soil burial tests over a 12-week period. This section discusses the decomposition kinetics as influenced by fiber concentration and compares the environmental breakdown rates of

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reinforced versus non-reinforced composites and EPS foam, emphasizing their ecological advantages.

Table 3

Comparative Mean Weight Loss Percentage

Specimen Group	Week 2 (%)	Week 4 (%)	Week 6 (%)	Week 8 (%)	Week 10 (%)	Week 12 (%)	Average Weekly Degradation Rate
Low-Density EPS Foam Control	1.28	2.56	3.85	6.41	8.97	10.26	0.86%
Non-abaca mycelium control	65.7	74.78	87.66	91.04	94.93	97.87	8.16%
10% Abaca	46.07	51.94	66.85	78.09	88.63	94.8	7.90%
20% Abaca	54.55	60.97	70.56	77.48	84.6	89.24	7.44%
30% Abaca	46.15	53.13	62	69.41	75.1	83.73	6.98%
40% Abaca	27.66	35.47	43.67	48.67	53.44	59.06	4.92%
50% Abaca	17.53	24.27	28.8	36.55	39.65	41.97	3.50%

As seen in table 3, the incorporation of Abaca fiber established an inverse relationship between reinforcement level and degradation. As fiber concentration increased, the average weekly rate systematically decreased.

The non-abaca mycelium composite control set the maximum baseline rate, achieving near-complete degradation (97.87%) with an average weekly rate of 8.16%. In

contrast, the low-density EPS foam control was expected to be the stable non-biodegradable benchmark, degrading at a negligible rate of 0.86% per week. The mechanically optimal 30% abaca composite exhibited an average weekly weight loss of 6.98%, which is approximately 14.5% lower than the non-abaca composite control (8.16% per week), indicating a modest reduction in biodegradation rate at this fiber loading.

While the 10% and 20% groups maintained high efficiency (7.90% and 7.44% per week), the rate diminished progressively with higher fiber loading. This deceleration can be observed in the high-level reinforcements (40% and 50%), where rates dropped to 4.92% and 3.50% per week. In a similar study, Ghazvinian and Gürsoy (2022) found that mycelium composites decompose rapidly due to their organic structure and high microbial accessibility, supporting the substantial weight loss seen in all mycelium composite groups. Nevertheless, all composite maintained degradation rates 4 to 9 times faster than the low-density EPS foam control, confirming their strong suitability for a sustainable end-of-life cycle.

Table 4

Significant Difference in the Tensile Strength

Control	Abaca Fiber Concentration	Mean Difference (kg/cm²)	Sig. (p-value)	Interpretation
Non-Abaca mycelium composite	10%	-2.73	0.10	Not significant
	20%	-4.16	0.01*	Significant
	30%	-8.31	0.00*	Significant
	40%	-5.42	0.00*	Significant
	50%	-4.10	0.01*	Significant
Low-Density EPS Foam	10%	11.21	0.00*	Significant
	20%	9.77	0.00*	Significant
	30%	5.63	0.00*	Significant
	40%	8.52	0.00*	Significant
	50%	9.84	0.00*	Significant

p-value ≤ 0.05 is significant*

Table 4 shows that the addition of abaca fiber produced a significant improvement in the tensile strength of the mycelium composites beginning at 20%, with the strongest enhancement observed at 30% abaca. According to Elsacker et al. (2019), natural fibers reinforce mycelium composites by improving internal stress transfer, which helps explain why tensile strength increased starting at 20% abaca and peaking at 30%. This concentration yielded the highest increase in strength compared to the non-abaca control, indicating that 30% provides the most effective reinforcement where the mycelium–fiber bonding is optimal. Although the 40% and 50% treatments also demonstrated significant difference, their tensile values were lower than those at 30%, suggesting that excessive fiber loading

may disrupt the mycelial matrix and reduce bonding efficiency. Aiduang et al. (2024) and Paglicawan et al. (2021) confirm that excessive fiber content can disrupt matrix continuity and reduce bonding efficiency, leading to decreased tensile strength beyond an optimal fiber concentration.

Compared to low-density EPS foam, all composite samples remained mechanically inferior, aligning with Enarevba & Haapala (2023) showing that mycelium-based materials exhibit lower tensile strength than synthetic foams. Overall, the data confirm that while abaca fiber enhances the mechanical performance of the mycelium composite, the effect follows a non-linear pattern, with 30% emerging as the optimal formulation.

Table 5

Significant Difference in Water Absorption

Control	Abaca Fiber Concentration	Mean Difference (%)	Sig. (p-value)	Interpretation
Non-Abaca mycelium composite	10%	69.00	0.60	not significant
	20%	43.30	0.92	not significant
	30%	-5.38	1.00	not significant
	40%	-1.81	1.00	not significant
	50%	-3.55	1.00	not significant
Low-Density EPS Foam	10%	-219.28	0.00*	Significant
	20%	-244.98	0.00*	Significant
	30%	-293.66	0.00*	Significant
	40%	-290.08	0.00*	Significant
	50%	-291.83	0.00*	Significant

p-value ≤ 0.05 is significant*

The results for water absorption indicate that none of the abaca-reinforced mycelium composites exhibited a statistically significant difference compared to the non-abaca mycelium control, as reflected by the consistently high p-values ($p > 0.05$) across all fiber concentrations.

Although numerical variations were observed such as the lower mean absorption at 10% abaca and the higher, more variable values at 30% to 50% fiber loading, these differences were not strong enough to be statistically significant. This outcome suggests that increasing abaca fiber content does not reliably reduce or increase water absorption within the tested range, and that the hydrophilic, porous nature of the mycelium–sawdust matrix remains the dominant factor influencing moisture uptake. This uniformity across treatments is consistent with Monsalve (2025) findings that the hydrophilic behavior of mycelium materials is strongly tied to their microstructural characteristics, where lower densities and open pore networks encourage moisture penetration regardless of added fibers.

In contrast, all mycelium-based samples showed highly significant differences when compared with Low-Density EPS foam, confirming that EPS absorbs virtually no water while the biocomposites exhibit inherently high moisture susceptibility. Overall, the findings demonstrate that abaca reinforcement improves mechanical strength but does not provide a measurable advantage in water resistance under the PNS ISO 16893:2017 conditions.

Table 6

Significant Difference in the Decomposition Rate

Control (non-abaca composite)	Abaca Fiber Concentration	Mean Difference (%)	Sig. (p-value)	Interpretation
Non-Abaca mycelium composite	10%	14.27	0.48	Not significant
	20%	12.43	0.64	Not significant
	30%	20.41	0.12	Not significant
	40%	40.67	0*	Significant
	50%	53.87	0*	Significant
Low-Density EPS Foam	10%	-65.51	0*	Significant
	20%	-67.35	0*	Significant
	30%	-59.37	0*	Significant
	40%	-39.11	0*	Significant
	50%	-25.91	0.02*	Significant

p-value ≤ 0.05 is significant*

The results in Table 6 show that the 10%, 20%, and 30% abaca composites did not show a significant difference in decomposition rate compared with the non-abaca composite ($p > 0.05$). This means that this fiber reinforcement did not substantially slow biodegradation, and these formulations decomposed at rates similar to the non-abaca mycelium composite control. In contrast, the 40% and 50% abaca composites displayed highly significant differences, reflecting a marked reduction in degradation rate. According to Paglicawan et al. (2021) and Aiduang et al. (2024), the slower breakdown at higher fiber loadings occurs because dense fiber packing increases structural rigidity and reduces the surface area available for microbial degradation, causing the composite to persist longer in soil.

When compared with EPS foam, all mycelium-based samples showed significantly higher decomposition percentages, confirming their strong biodegradability advantage regardless of fiber concentration. Per Ghazvinian and Gürsoy (2022), the results indicate that while increasing abaca content can delay decomposition, especially at 40–50%, the material remains far more environmentally degradable than conventional synthetic packaging.

CHAPTER IV
SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECCOMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of the research, conclusions, and recommendations for future studies. The findings included in this chapter are based on the performed data analysis.

Summary

The study measured the tensile strength, water absorption, and decomposition rates of mycelium–abaca composites across different abaca concentrations (10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50%) and compared to non-abaca mycelium composite and low-density EPS foam. All composites were prepared under standardized conditions, molded, dried, and subjected to tensile strength and water absorption testing at DOST-FPRDI, while biodegradation was assessed through a 12-week soil burial experiment.

Tensile testing showed that durability varied with abaca content, confirming that composite stress resistance depended on fiber loading. Water absorption

remained uniformly high for all formulations, consistent with the hydrophilic mycelium–sawdust matrix. Soil burial produced steady mass loss in every biocomposite over 12 weeks, with the rate of degradation influenced by fiber concentration. In contrast, EPS foam exhibited negligible changes in strength or mass and absorbed virtually no water across the same testing period.

Conclusion

1. An increase in tensile strength relative to non-abaca mycelium control was observed for the 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% abaca, with 30% abaca emerging as the optimal reinforcement level. Water absorption remained high across all treatments and similar from the non-abaca mycelium control. The addition of abaca fibers did not reduce the hydrophilicity of the composite, indicating that moisture uptake is influenced by the porous nature of the mycelium–sawdust matrix rather than fiber concentration.
2. All mycelium–abaca composites degraded rapidly over 12 weeks, with much higher weekly weight loss than EPS foam. The non-abaca control decomposed fastest ($\approx 8\%$ weight loss per week), nearly fully degrading by week 12. The 10%, 20%, and 30% abaca composites followed similar trajectories, with only slight reductions in degradation ($\approx 7-7.5\%$ per week). In contrast, the 40% and 50% abaca formulations decayed substantially more slowly, at roughly 5% and $<4\%$ per week, respectively, indicating that higher fiber loading limits microbial penetration and slows mass loss.

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3. A statistically significant improvement in tensile strength was observed for the 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% abaca treatments relative to the non-abaca control, with 30% abaca emerging as the optimal reinforcement level. No significant differences were found in water absorption among all mycelium-based groups, confirming that abaca concentration does not affect moisture uptake.
4. The 10%, 20%, and 30% abaca composites showed no significant difference in decomposition compared with the non-abaca mycelium composite, indicating that moderate fiber loadings do not impair biodegradability. In contrast, 40% and 50% abaca composites showed significant difference in decomposition compared with the non-abaca mycelium composite, demonstrating that high fiber concentration noticeably hinders soil breakdown. All mycelium-based composites decomposed significantly faster than EPS foam.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the research study, in consideration of the scope & limitations, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Use Liquid Culture (LC) inoculation with injected, highly active mycelial fragments and compare its performance to solid-grain inoculation for the optimized 30% abaca composite.
2. Test alternative local substrates such as rice husk, coconut coir, sugarcane bagasse combined with the 30% abaca formulation to assess how substrate type affects colonization, mechanical properties, and density.

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3. Improve surface hydrophobicity by applying natural coatings such as beeswax, shellac, bio-waxes to the 30% abaca composite and quantifying changes in water absorption and strength.
4. Assess long-term mechanical stability by repeating internal bond (tensile strength) tests on samples stored for 6–12 months to track aging of the mycelial matrix.
5. Optimize post-processing densification through higher hot-press temperatures, pressures, and dwell times to reduce porosity, lower water uptake, and increase strength toward high-density EPS or cardboard levels.
6. Extend decomposition tests from 12 weeks to at least 26 weeks (6 months) to obtain a full degradation curve and estimate the composite's half-life in soil.
7. Extend incubation time beyond 22 days and monitor mycelial density to determine the incubation period that maximizes mechanical performance without overgrowth or contamination.
8. Standardize particle size of sawdust and abaca fibers using sieving so that fiber length and diameter are consistent, minimizing noise from packing and porosity differences.

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